

Author Rights Publishing Agreement Analysis: Optional Exercise

Instructions:

Based on our discussion today in Session 2 about author rights considerations, please use the list of publications below and:

- Read the publishing agreements
- Pick one, and
- Flag any of the language that you think would bear reconsideration or negotiation before you would sign the agreement to publish with the journal.

Keep in mind an author's rights to their original work once it is in a fixed form; that is, the right to reproduce, prepare derivative works, distribute copies, perform, and display the work.

Also keep in mind that transferring copyright or granting a license doesn't have to be all or nothing. You may want to ask yourself some of the questions below as you are reading the agreements:

- Can I make copies for my own lectures or classroom instruction?
- Can I post the work on my university/research website or in a repository?
- Can I distribute my work to colleagues and/or students who request a copy?
- Can I use this in my thesis, dissertation, or other scholarly publication?
- Can I alter the work, update it, and add to it?

Once you have completed your review, please consider sharing your impressions with the group via Slack.

Bonus points for sharing how you might approach this conversation. (With apologies for the North American -centric publications; we are all residents of North America.

Publishing Agreements:

Journal of the American Medical Association:

https://jamanetwork.com/DocumentLibrary/InstructionsForAuthors/JAMA/against_crit.pdf

Wiley:

<https://authorservices.wiley.com/asset/Copyright-Transfer-Agreement-Sample.pdf>

OR <https://authorservices.wiley.com/asset/Exclusive-License-Agreement-Sample.pdf>

Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication:

<https://jlsclib.org/about/submissions/>

Author Rights Exercise: Session Two Optional Exercise

Credit and Attribution:

Acknowledgment. Adapted for this context with thanks to Kyle K. Courtney, Copyright Advisor, Harvard Office for Scholarly Communication for permission to use this exercise. Courtney, Kyle K. & Quilter, Laura. "Presentation Copyright Bootcamp #1: Open Access, Nonexclusive Licensing, and Author Rights." Presentation at Association of College & Research Libraries New England Chapter Scholarly Communication Interest Group, Worcester, MA, January 2019.

If you use our exercise, please let us know, and please cite this as:
Bordalejo, B., Page, A., Kilcer, E. (2020). Author Rights Publishing Agreement Analysis.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> or send a letter to Creative Commons, PO Box 1866, Mountain View, CA 94042, USA